

Fluorescent Brightening Agents*

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The dyestuff industry has witnessed many important and epoch-making discoveries during the last sixty-five years. Hardly had the twentieth century begun, when Rene' Bohn discovered Indanthrene, the first vat dyestuff of the anthraquinone series in 1901. This virgin field was developed for nearly twenty years firstly by German and then by British Chemists very successfully and culminated in the discovery of Caledon, Jade Green by Fraser-Thomson in 1920, and of Indigosols by Bader and Sunder in 1921. The azoic dyes represented by Naphthol A. S. and its congeners, the Neolans or pre-chromed dyes, the stabilised diazo salts, and the mixtures of these diazosalts with compounds of the Naphthol A. S. series for printing were great milestones in azo colouring matters during the same period. An entirely new tinctorial structure was discovered in 1932 by Linstead and his co-workers in phthalocyanine, and though insoluble in water, subsequent research in this field led to its use as printing dyes (Alcian Blue) and vat dyes. In 1956, the fibre-reactive dyes (procions) were put on the market by I.C.I. to commemorate the centenary Jubilee of Sir W. H. Perkin, the discoverer of the first synthetic dyestuff Mauve in 1856, and this was followed quickly by a host of other brands, *e.g.*, Cibacrons (C.I.B.A.), Remazoles (Hoechst), Reactones (Geigy), Drimarenes (Sandoz) and Lavafix (Bayers) etc. Commercial Fluorescent Brightening Agents or Optical Whitening Agents were discovered by Wendt in 1940 when he found that some acyl derivatives of 4 : 4'-diaminostilbene-2 : 2'-disulphonic acid imparted permanent whiteness by giving fluorescent effects to textiles and paper. These optical whitening agents had far greater impact on the public than any of the discoveries described above. The chemists gave the business world a gift of advertising. In fact, the public has become accustomed to an entirely new standard of whiteness, and brightness in textiles and paper. Not only have the range and sale of these products been enormous during the last twenty five years, but their uses have also been extended to all sorts of fabrics (natural as well as synthetic), textile processing, detergent industries, the manufacture of paper, the plastics, polishes, cosmetics and hair-lotions.

Natural as well as synthetic white fibres acquire a slight yellowish tinge during their use and this becomes much stronger if this fault is not corrected. There are different methods of removing this yellow tinge. The first one is the chemical method of bleaching by chlorine or sulphur dioxide. The second method consists in the addition of a small amount of ultramarine or indigo, which absorbs the yellow light and makes up for the blue light absorbed by the yellow colour of the untreated fabric. The fabric, therefore, appears white, but the total amount of light reflected is reduced with a consequent reduction in luminosity. The

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third method consists in increasing the amount of blue radiation in the light reflected by the fabric by treating it with a small quantity of a fluorescent substance which generates blue light. The fabric appears whiter as the yellowish colour is corrected by the addition of blue light. The total light reflected from the fabric is greater with the consequent increase in luminosity. The substances which are thus added are called Fluorescent Brightening Agents or Optical Whitening Agents¹.

They are colourless dyestuffs, substantive to the fabrics and are effective in small concentrations of about 0.01–0.1 per cent by weight on the weight of the fabric. They absorb light in the ultraviolet region in the range of 335–365 $m\mu$ and emit them at longer wavelength in the blue visible region somewhere near 450 $m\mu$. Their fluorescence varies from a reddish to a greenish and neutral blue. The fluorescence of a compound depends upon its chemical nature and may be changed by the introduction of substituents. Nitrogen and oxygen in the ring system and hydroxy, amino, alkyl and alkoxy groups as substituents usually promote fluorescence, while nitro and azo groups retard it². Double bonds, conjugated with aromatic nuclei have a marked effect on fluorescence of aromatic compounds. Stilbene is a typical example. The compound must be planar and should contain electron-donating groups such as OH, NH₂, OCH₃ and should be free from electron-accepting groups such as NO₂, N–N etc. It should also contain a system of conjugated double bonds³.

As our main interest has been in the chemical constitution of the fluorescent brightening agents, a brief review of the various types of compounds which have been shown to behave this way will be made. They can be broadly divided into (A) Heterocyclic compounds and (B) Derivatives of stilbene. The Heterocyclic compounds can be further classified into those containing (a) Five membered rings, (b) Six membered rings, (c) Fused rings (d) Linked rings.

Five membered rings may contain only one heteroatom such as the pyrroles, the fluorenes, and the thiophenes. These rings fused with benzene rings include some good optical brightening agents. The derivatives of 2:3-diphenyl indole⁴ (I), 2-phenylbenzothiophene-1:1-dioxide⁵ (II), 2-phenylnaphthiophenes-1:1-dioxide⁶ (III), dibenzothiophene dioxide (IV) specially 3:7-diamino dibenzothiophene dioxide⁷ (V) and 3:7-diaminofluorenes⁸ (VI) are striking examples of this type of substances.

1. D. A. W. Adams, *J. Soc. Dyer. Col.*, 1959, 75, 22.
2. M. Dummenberger, *CIBA Review*, 1960, 140, 32.
3. C. W. Bridges and R. T. William's *Nature*, 1962, 196, 61.
4. U. S. Patents, 2845, 436 and 2845, 437; East German Patent 20468.
5. Ger. Patent, 1063, 571; B.P. 879, 610.
6. B. P. 871, 351.
7. U. P. Patents, 2568, 493; B.P. 884, 482; U.S. Patent, 2619, 470; 3031, 460; 2911, 415.
8. U.S. Patent, 2662, 913.

The rings with two heteroatoms include the derivatives of pyrazole (VII) imidazole, oxazole and thiazole. Pyrazolines (VIII) have also been claimed as good brighteners⁹.

Oxazoles, benzoxazoles (IX) imidazoles, benzimidazoles (X) thiazoles, and benzthiazoles (XI) have been used as fluorescent bleaching agents¹⁰. The oxadiazoles (XII) and the thiaziazole (XIII) have been used as optical brightening agents for certain fibres.

Benzotriazole (XIV) and naphthotriazole (XV) derivatives have proved to be good brighteners, the fluorescence being blue. They are stable to hypochlorite bleaching and possess good light fastness¹¹.

9. U.S. Patent, 2740, 793; B.P. 808, 118; 832, 239.

10. B.P. 772, 543; U.S. Patent, 3030, 224, Ger. Pat., 1019, 690.

11. G.P., 1088, 660; Swiss Pat. 356, 557.

The pyridine and quinoline derivatives are good optical brighteners exhibiting a blue fluorescence and are stable to hypochlorite¹². 7:8-dihydroxy coumarin or aesculetin was

found to be the first brightener by P. Kraiss¹³ in 1929. Umbelliferone acetate was claimed as a fluorescent brightener by Ultrazelle G.M.B.H. (Germany). Similarly 4-methyl-umbelliferone was claimed by H. Meyer¹⁴ in 1939. Most of the coumarins having a hydroxy, amino or dialkyl-amino groups as substituents in 7 position (XVI) have blue to greenish blue fluorescence and are suitable brighteners for cellulose acetate, nylon and other synthetic fibres¹⁵. The fluorescent whiteners having fused rings include triazolopyridines¹⁶ (XVII) and triazolopyrimidines¹⁷ (XVIII).

12. U.S.P. 2639, 990; G.P. 964, 861.

13. P. Kraiss, *Mell. Textilber*, 1929, **10**, 468.

14. H. Meyer, B.P. 427, 473; B. P. 522,672.

15. *Textile Recorder*, 1949, **67**, 68. also B.P. 655,258; 735,895; 862,286.

16. U. S. P., 3058, 989.

17. B. P., 876, 694

In order to have a better fluorescence and intensity, two heterocyclic rings can be linked together in the same molecule. The linking may be direct or through an intermediate which can increase the conjugation such as $-\text{CH}-$, $-\text{N}-$, $-\text{NH}$, and $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ etc. Examples are 7-hydroxy-coumarins having thienyl, pyrazolyl, benzoxazolyl and thiazolyl groups¹⁸ in 3 position. 7-thiazinyl coumarins, 3 : 7-di-triazinyl-dibenzothiophenes can be easily prepared and are good brighteners¹⁹. The most important brightening agents having two-heterocyclic rings linked by $-\text{CH}-\text{CH}-$ linkage (ethylene) are bis-benziminazolyl-, benzoxazolyl- or benzthiazolyl-ethylenes (XIX). They are fairly easy to prepare and give blue fluorescence²⁰.

They are specially good for synthetic fibres. A benzene ring can be used to link together twoazole rings. Thus 1 : 4-diazolyl-benzenes (XX) and 1 : 4 di-benzazolyl-benzones (XXI) are good brighteners for synthetic fibres²¹.

18. French Patent, 1320,597; B.P., 912,719.

19. U.S.P., 2945,033; 2845,423; G.P., 1102,694.

20. U.S.P., 2488,289; 2488,094; 2808,407, B.P., 803,361; 824,659; 600,096.

21. U.S., 2901,479; B.P. 722,543; 722,544.

Similarly naphthotriazoles can be linked to itself or to benzoxazole, benzthiazole and benzimidazole through the benzene ring²². They give blue fluorescence and whiten synthetic fibres. They are stable to hypochlorite and have a good light fastness. Finally the linkage of two heterocyclic rings can be made through a heterocyclic ring which may be a furan, a pyrrole, a thiophene or pyridine²³.

Derivatives of Stilbene

The first brighteners put on the market were the derivatives of 4 : 4'-diaminostilbene-2 : 2'-disulphonic acid, and were the bis-N-benzoyl derivatives of this acid²⁴. They are of the following four types (XXII) (a), (b), (c) and (d).

XXII (a)

XXII (b)

R—Aryl or substituted aryl groups, and Alkyl or hydroxyalkyl groups.

XXII (c)

XXII (d)

R = Aryl or substituted aryl.

R₁ = Alkyl or hydroxyalkyl.

22. U.S.P., 2700,044; 2666,062.

23. Bel.Pat., 610,558; 619,755; G.P., 1086,237; B.P. 879,610; 888,209.

24. BIOS Reports No. 259, 1088. F.I.A.T., 1302. P. Landolt, Amer. Dyestuff Reporter, 1949, 38, 353. I.C.I.B.P., 472,473; 580,205. I.G.S.P., 224,613. D. A. W. Adams, W. Wilson and I.C.I.B.P., 624,051; 624,052. Geigy B.P., 595,065. B. Wendt, D.R.P., 752,677.

Type XXII(b) gives a violet shade of white and is known as Blankophor R, while type XXII(c) gives a blue shade of white and is known as Blankophor B. Types XXII(d) are cheaper and easier to manufacture. The mixed type, an acyl-triazine derivative XXII(e) is also known.

R-C₆H₄OCH₃; CH₂-O-C₆H₅ etc.

X and Y are RNH, OR, Cl, etc.

This type gives less reddish fluorescence than the bistriazine type (XXIIc), and has better affinity for wool. All these stilbene derivatives have a poor light fastness and a moderately good resistance to hypochlorite. Their substantivity to cotton is improved when they include the triazine ring in the molecule.

Another type (XXIII) of diaminostilbene disulphonic acid derivative is made by tetrazotising it and coupling with a β -naphthylamine sulphonic acid or 1-naphthylamine-4-sulphonic acid and oxidising the *o*-aminoazo compound to the triazole²⁵. These products of which Blankophor G is an example are completely stable to bleaching, but the shade is on the green side. More neutral shades are obtained by having only one triazole ring present. Such compounds are obtained from 4'-amino-stilbene-2-sulphonic acid or its derivatives and are of the type (XXIV).

25. Farbenfabriken Bayer, B.P., 683,895.

These are bleach-stable and where no additional sulphonic acid groups are present, they also have affinity for nylon. The naphthalene ring can be replaced by a benzene ring, an acenaphthene ring or a heterocyclic ring like indazole²⁶. A. Yabe and M. Hayashi²⁷ have prepared a number of disodium 2-x-4-y-1 : 3 : 5-triazin-6-yl-2 : 2'-stilbene disulphonates (X and Y same or different and included OH, OCH₃, OC₂H₅, NH₂, NH.C₆H₅ or NH.C₆H₄SO₃Na). The absorption spectra of the aqueous solutions of these compounds in the range 220–420 m μ were studied. They also studied fluorescence intensity, light fastness and wash fastness. Unsymmetrical derivatives of 4 : 4'-diaminostilbene-2 : 2'-disulphonic acid represented by the general formula (XXV) were prepared by Hayakawa, M. Orida, S. Kabayashi and H. Hasui²⁸ by condensing 4-amino-4'-nitro-stilbene-2 : 2'-disulphonic acid with phenylisocyanate, reducing the nitro to the amino group which was made to react with one mole of cyanuric chloride. The two chlorine atoms were replaced by anilino, ethylamino, methoxy, phenoxy and other groups.

As unsymmetrical derivatives of 4 : 4'-diaminostilbene 2 : 2'-disulphonic acids were expected to give interesting results as fluorescent brightening agents and as conditions for the monophenyl ureidation were found by us and we thought it worthwhile to prepare them. They could be prepared from the easily accessible diamino derivatives, instead of the lengthy method of the Japanese workers. Phenyl-isocyanate and disodium 4 : 4'-diaminostilbene-2 : 2'-disulphonate reacted in aqueous solution at 20–25° under mechanical stirring to give the mono-ureido derivative, which was reacted with cyanuric chloride at 0°. The second chlorine was replaced at 25° by arylamino or alkylamino groups while the third chlorine was replaced by the same group at 60°. Thus a number of unsymmetrically substituted derivatives of 4 : 4'-diaminostilbene-2 : 2'-disulphonic acid represented by the general formula (XXV) were made. In these formulae R-C₆H₅, while R₁ and R₂ were equal or different, and were represented by anilino, monomethylamino, diethanolamino, benzylamino, butylamino, morpholino, α -naphthylamino, 2-pyridyl-amino and 4-sulphnaphthylamino, *m*-sulphanilino and *p*-sulphanilino groups.

We have also prepared some symmetrical derivatives of 4 : 4'-diaminostilbene-2 : 2'-disulphonic acids as they may prove to be interesting as fluorescent whitening agents. The symmetrical derivatives of the general formula (XXVI) have R₁-*m*-sulphanilino, *p*-sulphanilino, and 4-sulphnaphthylamino groups and R₂-anilino, diethylamino, diethanolamino,

26. Geigy B.P., 717,889; 763,696; 781,821. Hickson and Welch Ltd., Bel. Patent., 561,464. B.P. 828,329.
27. A. Yabe and M. Hayashi, C.A., 1959, 35, 7599, 8635, 5571, 16542.
28. G. Hayakawa, M. Orida, S. Kabayashi and H. Hasui, C.A., 1960, 54, 11495(d).

butylamino, morpholino, benzylamino, *o*-anisidino, *p*-anisidino, *m*-sulphanilino, and *p*-sulphanilino groups were prepared.

We also prepared the unsymmetrical compounds represented by the general formula (XXVII).

where $R_1 = R_2$ and was represented by the group

and R_3 was equal to anilino, monomethylanilino, diethanolamino, benzylamino, butylamino, α -naphthylamino, morpholino, 2-pyridylamino and 4-sulphnaphthyl-1-amino groups. Finally a symmetrical compound was prepared where R_1 , R_2 and R_3 were all equal. The manufacture of these fluorescent whitening agents has been patented by us²⁹.

The ultraviolet absorption spectra of the sodium salts of these compounds in water were studied by us during the intervals of 0, 24, and 48 hr. to test the stability of their solutions using the Beckmann D. U. spectrophotometer. The dyeing of cellulose cloth was carried out with their 0.02 to 0.06 per cent solutions, and the whiteness imparted to the cloth was found to be comparable with that imparted by Geigy's standard substances Blankophor R (Reddish fluorescence) and Blankophor B. V. N. (Blue fluorescence). The percentage of the solutions giving the same whiteness (visual comparison) as given by 0.06 per cent solutions

29. R. D. Desai, (Miss) S. K. Dalal and A. R. Parikh, Indian Patents, 86741 and 90380 of 1963 and 87818 of 1965.

of Geigy's standard samples have been given below in Tables I, II and III. The efficiency to impart whiteness is shown by grades *a*, *b*, and *c*, where, '*a*' denotes superiority to Geigy's standard samples Blankophor BVN or Blankophor R, '*b*' denotes equality and '*c*' shows inferiority. It is fairly clear that the symmetrical compounds 9 and 18 under Table I, and unsymmetrical compounds 31, 33, 38, 39, 44, 46 and 47 under Table II are superior to Geigy's standard substances Blankophor R and Blankophor B.V.N. on the market. It will be, therefore, worthwhile to subject these compounds to further scrutiny. Moreover, it is encouraging that out of seventy samples of fluorescent brightening agents prepared, nine are superior, nineteen are equal and fortytwo are inferior to the two standard Geigy products which are in general use in industry.

TABLE I
Symmetrical Fluorescent Brightening Agents (XXVI)

Sr.No. of Comp.	R ₁	R ₂	Type of fluorescence	Equivalent to respec- tive sample of Geigy's 0.06%	Efficiency to impart whiteness
1	4-Sulphnaphthylamino	Chloro	Bluish	—	—
2	4-Sulphnaphthylamino	Morpholino	Reddish	0.065	b
3	4-Sulphnaphthylamino	Diethanolamino	Reddish	0.060	b
4	4-Sulphnaphthylamino	Benzylamino	Bluish	0.075	c
5	4-Sulphnaphthylamino	Butylamino	Bluish	0.080	c
6	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Chloro	Bluish	—	—
7	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Anilino	Bluish	0.060	b
8	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Morpholino	Reddish	0.060	b
9	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Diethanolamino	Reddish	0.050	a
10	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Butylamino	Bluish	0.075	c
11	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>o</i> -Anisidino	Bluish	0.075	c
12	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>p</i> -Anisidino	Bluish	0.075	c
13	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Diethylanilino	Bluish	0.080	c
14	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Chloro	Bluish	—	—
15	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Bluish	0.070	c
16	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Anilino	Bluish	0.060	b
17	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Morpholino	Bluish	0.065	b
18	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Diethanolamino	Reddish	0.055	a
19	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Benzylamino	Bluish	0.075	c
20	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Butylamino	Bluish	0.085	c
21	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>o</i> -Anisidino	Bluish	0.070	c
22	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>p</i> -Anisidino	Bluish	0.070	c
23	Anilino	Chloro	Bluish	—	—
24	Anilino	Diethanolamino	Bluish	0.060	b
25	Diethanolamino	Chloro	Bluish	—	—
26	Diethanolamino	Diethanolamino	Bluish	0.065	b
27	Diethanolamino	Butylamino	Bluish	0.070	c

TABLE II
Unsymmetrical Fluorescent Compounds (XXV)

Sr.No. of Comp.	R ₁	R ₂	Type of fluorescence	Equivalent to respective sample of Geigy's 0.06%	Efficiency to impart whiteness
28	Disodium-4-phenylureido-4'-amino-stilbene-2 : 2'-disulphonate		Bluish	—	—
29	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Chloro	Bluish	—	—
30	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Chloro	Bluish	—	—
31	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Anilino	Bluish	0.050	a
32	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Morpholino	Reddish	0.060	b
33	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Diethanolamino	Reddish	0.055	a
34	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>o</i> -Anisidino	Bluish	0.065	b
35	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Benzylamino	Bluish	0.075	c
36	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Butylamino	Bluish	0.080	c
37	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Anilino	Bluish	0.060	b
38	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Morpholino	Bluish	0.055	a
39	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Diethanolamino	Reddish	0.055	a
40	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>o</i> -Anisidino	Bluish	0.070	c
41	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Butylamino	Bluish	0.070	c
42	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Benzylamino	Bluish	0.080	c
43	Cl	Anilino	—	—	—
44	Anilino	Anilino	Bluish	0.035	a
45	Monoethanolamino	Anilino	Bluish	0.070	b
46	Diethanol amino	Anilino	Bluish	0.030	a
47	Morpholino	Anilino	Bluish	0.040	a
48	-OH	Anilino	Reddish	0.060	b
49	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	Anilino	Bluish	0.065	b
50	Cl	Diethanolamino	—	—	—
51	Benzylamino	Diethanolamino	Reddish	0.070	c
52	Butylamino	Diethanolamino	Bluish	0.075	c
53	4-Sulphnaphthyl-amino	Diethanolamino	Reddish	0.060	b
54	Cl	Benzylamino	—	—	—
55	Benzylamino	Benzylamino	Bluish	0.080	c
56	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	Benzylamino	Bluish	0.070	c
57	Cl	Monomethyl-anilino	—	—	—
58	Monomethylanilino	Monomethyl-anilino	Bluish	0.070	c
59	Cl	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	—	—	—
60	Morpholino	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	Reddish	0.060	b
61	Anisidino	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	Bluish	0.070	c
62	Butylamino	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	Slight Bluish	0.080	c

TABLE III

Unsymmetrical Derivatives (XXVII)

Sr.No. of Comp.	R ₁	R ₂	Type of fluorescence	Equivalent to respec- tive sample of Geigy's 0.06%	Efficiency to impart whiteness
63	Cl	R ₁	—	—	—
64	Anilino	R ₁	Bluish	0.070	c
65	Morpholino	R ₁	Reddish	0.060	b
66	1-Naphthylamino	R ₁	Bluish	0.070	c
67	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	R ₁	Bluish	0.070	c
68	Diethanolamino	R ₁	Reddish	0.065	b
69	2-Pyridylamino	R ₁	Bluish	0.075	c
70	R ₁	R ₁	Bluish	0.065	b

Simple substituted derivatives of cyanuric chloride were prepared as we wanted to ascertain the effect of the substituents on the *s*-triazine ring which was present in most of the fluorescent whitening agents described above, by studying their ultraviolet absorption spectra. The general procedure was the same as adopted above. The general formula of these compounds was 2R₁-4R₂-6R₃-*S*-triazine (XXVII) and Table IV gives the summary of the trisubstituted triazines prepared by us.

TABLE IV

2 : 4 : 6-trisubstituted-S-triazines

Sr.No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
71	Cl	Cl	Anilino
72	Cl	Anilino	Anilino
73	Anilino	Anilino	Anilino
74	Cl	Morpholino	Anilino
75	Cl	Diethanolamino	Anilino
76	Cl	Benzylamino	Anilino
77	Cl	Butylamino	Anilino
78	Cl	2-Pyridyl-amino	Anilino
79	Butylamino	Butylamino	Anilino
80	Diethanolamino	Diethanolamino	Anilino
81	Cl	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Anilino
82	Cl	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Anilino
83	Cl	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	Anilino
84	Cl	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino
85	Cl	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino
86	Cl	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino
87	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino
88	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino
89	4-Sulphanathyl-1-amino	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino
90	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>m</i> -Sulphanilino	Anilino
91	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	<i>p</i> -Sulphanilino	Anilino
92	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	4-Sulphnaphthyl-1-amino	Anilino

From the study of the ultraviolet absorption spectra of the mono-, di-, and tri-substituted derivatives of S-1 : 3 : 5-triazines, and the symmetrical and unsymmetrical fluorescent brightening agents recorded in tables IV, I and II, the following discussions and conclusions can be arrived at.

2 : 4-Dichloro-6-anilino-s-triazine has the absorption maximum at $\lambda 263 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 4.20$). This absorption maximum is shifted to $\lambda 268 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 3.5304$) in the case of 2-chloro-4 : 6-dianilino-s-triazine and to $\lambda 271 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 3.12$) in the case of 2 : 4 : 6-trianilino-s-triazine. Thus the systematic replacement of chlorine by the anilino group leads to a slight bathochromic and hypochromic effect. If instead of the anilino group, diethanolamino, butylamino, benzylamino and 2-pyridyl-amino groups are used, bathochromic effects of the same magnitude are seen. However, if the anilino group is replaced by *m*-sulphanilino, *p*-sulphanilino, and 4-sulphnaphthyl-1-amino groups, the bathochromic effect is fairly good. The 2-chloro-4-*m*-sulphanilino-6-anilino-s-triazine has the absorption maximum at $\lambda 272 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 3.3434$); 2-chloro-4-*p*-sulphanilino-6-anilino-s-triazine has it at $\lambda 282 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 2.6428$) and 2-chloro-4-sulphnaphthylamino-6-anilino-s-triazine has it at $\lambda 295 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 2.8012$), was compared with the absorption at $\lambda \text{ max. } 262 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 4.2$). The replacement of three chlorine atoms by three anilino groups in s-triazine molecule i.e., the trianilino derivative gives the substance having the absorption maximum at $\lambda 271 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 3.12$) while tri-*m*-sulphanilino compound has the maximum at $\lambda 275 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 3.77$); tri-*p*-sulphanilino derivative has at $\lambda 288 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 4.20$) and tri-sulphnaphthyl-1-amino derivative at $\lambda 305 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 3.4045$). The bathochromic as well as hyperchromic effect of sulphnaphthyl-1-amino group is greater than that of *p*-sulphanilino group which is greater than that of *m*-sulphanilino group, which is greater than that of the anilino group.

The unsymmetrical fluorescent brightening agents (XXV) described in this section can be looked upon as 2 : 4 : 6-tri-substituted derivatives of 1 : 3 : 5-s-triazine (XXVII) where one of the substituents R_1 is 4-phenylureido-4'-amino-stilbene-2 : 2'-disulphonic acid group, and R_2 and R_3 may be varied. They can be thus correlated with the triazines described earlier. Let us discuss the compound 2 : 4-dianilino-6-chloro-s-triazine which has the absorption maximum at $\lambda 268 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 3.5304$). When Cl is replaced by R_1 , the absorption maximum is shifted to $\lambda 265 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 4.6433$). Thus there is the bathochromic and hyperchromic effect of R_1 . 2-Anilino-4-morpholino-6-chloro-s-triazine has the absorption maximum at $\lambda 260 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 2.9573$), while the compound obtained by the replacement of Cl by R_1 , the absorption maximum is shifted to $\lambda 350 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 3.8420$). Here again the effect of R_1 is bathochromic and hyperchromic. Similar arguments can be applied to other compounds. When the absorption of these compounds is examined at the intervals of 0, 24 and 48 hours, it is found that in some cases the absorption maximum is the highest in the beginning and falls regularly after 24 and 48 hours (Compound 44 of Table II). However, in most of the cases, the absorption maximum is highest in the beginning, falls after 24 hours and rises again after 48 hours. The difference in the extinction coefficient is also very slight. There is one additional point to be observed in the case of compound 47 of Table II and other compounds of its type. It has three absorption maxima $\lambda 350 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon = 3.8481$) : $\lambda 270 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log E = 3.8421$) and $\lambda 240 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log E = 3.9014$). The first one is

due to the stilbene conjugated system. The second and third maximum are due to the triazine ring, unsubstituted as well as substituted by aromatic groups.

As far as the symmetrical derivatives are concerned, there is a change in the absorption maximum. As for example in the case of the compound (2) of Table I, it falls down from λ max. 345 m μ ($\log \epsilon = 4.7883$) to λ max. 330 m μ ($\log \epsilon = 4.6935$) after 24 hours, and increases to λ max. 335 m μ ($\log \epsilon = 4.7249$) after 48 hours. Similarly, there is a drop in the intensity after 24 hours, but it rises after 48 hours. To sum up, there is practically very little difference between the symmetrical and unsymmetrical fluorescent brightening agents obtained from 4 : 4'-diamino-stilbene-2 : 2'-disulphonic acid with regard to the ultra-violet absorption spectra.

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30. A. R. Parikh, Ph.D. Thesis, Gujarat University, 1966.

31. Miss S. K. Dalal, Ph.D. Thesis, Gujarat University, 1966.